

ISic1371

I.Sicily inscription 1371

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140876

1. ἄ [γ] ρ,ρασία [τόπου]

2. παρὰ Χαρμ [ίδου]

3. κὲ Σοφίας· ἠ[γόρα]-

4. σεν δὲ Ἴρωμ [ανός]

5. [σ]ὺν Ἀγάθη [γυνεκί].

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492984

EDCS 39101751

PHI 140876

Bibliography

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